

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

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Abstract

During forward Pollicy, British forces faced strong resistance in the Tribal Area of Dera Ghazi Khan then the British statesmen revisit their strategy and they decided to engage the tribal chiefs with new political diplomacy through different types of motivation i.e administrative heads of their areas, lands and money as bribe. When British government negotiated with the inhabiting tribes and signed a treaty with different tribal chiefs and formed a new political system. This system was recognized as the Tumandari System in Dera Ghazi Khan. Tumandari System had a great similarity with the feudal system of Europe and this Tumandari System was infact a type of feudalism. These tumandars became the supporters and right hands of British Government for revenue collection as well as strategic partners. This paper highlights the socio-political impacts of the feudalism on the society of Dera Ghazi Khan.

Keywords: Feudalism, Subcontinent, Robert Sundeman, Tumandari System etc.

Introduction

The paper primarily deals with feudalism in Dera Ghazi Khan. When British Government occupied this region they appointed the tribal-heads as revenue collector with a new name as Tumandar. Tumandari System created a gulf of class stratification in the society and proved to be a catalyst of social and economic misery in the region. This system was legitimated and the these feudals were granted through Magistaarial powers as honorary Magistrate to strengthen them. while politically the tribal chiefs and their families are still considered the major players and the winning horse in their electoral constituencies in the regional politics of Dera Ghazi Khan.

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

Historical Perspective of Feudalism

Feudalism was derived from Feu, Feud or Feudum. That was a form of property which is found in books of Middle Ages. In French it became feodalite. It was named 'Fief' before that. When William the conqueror (1066-1135) conquered it and distributed the properties it was called 'Fief'. In Europe these rules were called Feudal rules and they had different types of properties. The famous book in this connection is 'Libri Feudorum'. Its author was an Italian who had collected all the rules and regulations, customs and traditions regarding 'Fief' like the beginning of Feudalism, its provision to someone, its confiscation and so on. In this it was clear that a woman could not hold this kind of property because they were not expected to provide military services.¹ The origin of feudalism is with the fall of the Roman Empire when the Germans occupied its scattered territories and subjugated its resources. After that feudal system spread throughout Europe and one of the reasons for the expansion of the feudal system was the racial and religious wars that engulfed many European countries. As a result, social stratification took place and its subjects were divided into classes.² In Europe, feudal lords formed a parallel government. Even the king became their ally because the king did not have the resources left and he was at the mercy of these feudal lords. The French Revolution crushed the feudal system in Europe and thus gradually the feudal system in Europe came to an end.³ India has been a scattered society since ancient times. The practice of farming here dates back to the Dravidian period as it was the Dravidians who made farming their livelihood. But later Arya came here and laid the foundation of a new system. The economic situation here also began to change. As a result of the Aryan caste system, the agricultural system in India changed and the local tribes began to be more and more attracted to farming.⁴

Feudalism In Dera Ghazi Khan.

The British needed a strong and influential people to support them who would help to stabilize their government. The mastermind of feudalism in the subcontinent during the imperialist era was Cornwallis who had the British model in mind. There was a need to create a class that would help in amassing the resources here, especially financial resources. For this, a permanent class of feudal lords was proposed by Lord Cornwallis and first it created in Bengal and they were contracted to collect revenue.⁵ In 1866 Sandeman was appointed Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan and he worked on British Forward Policy. With the establishment of the Border Military Force, Sandeman planned to occupy more territory under the Forward Policy. In order to capture the tribes, an attempt was made by the local chiefs to control their people. These chiefs were awarded large estates and cash.⁶ After successful negotiation Sandeman appointed various tribal leaders of Dera Ghazi Khan as Tamandar, whose appointment was not only a blow to their unity but also an effective strategy to divide them.⁷ The British statemen not only divided these tribes but also eliminated their resistance and paved the way for the advancement towards Balochistan in order to increase their holdings. They also strengthened the feudal class for its own interests. In Dera Ghazi Khan British Government wanted to preserve the *Sardari* System and tribal structure. Therefore, Government supported to strength the Tumandar. Therefore, to enhance the status of these Tumandar with magisterial powers conferred upon them and even given them the rights to collect revenue or other government dues from tribesmen. In

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

order to enable Tumandars to keep up this assignment, government granted them *Inams*, leases over vast lands as jagirs, squares of lands in colony areas of Punjab.⁸

The important functions of the duty of Tumandars were in their tuman as following;

- a. Collection of all government dues.
- b. Assistance to the administration in the maintenance of law and order on the frontier.
- c. Decision of Cases as *Ilaqa Magistrates* and subordinate judges.
- d. Jirga power and settlement of disputes through Jirgas.⁹

In 1926 with Jagir *Inams*, supplementary *Inams* were also granted in cash. Almost 26000 acres land was granted while average 15 acres were granted in colony districts by provincial government under Crown Grants of Land Act 1895. Some other lands were also granted to these Tumandars under the Colonization of Punjab Land Act 1912 and total granted 155 squares.¹⁰

Concession to Tumandars

Sr.#	Tuman	Cash	Land Squares
1	Khetran (Rais)	600/-	05
2	Qaisrani	3500/-	15
3	Buzdar	1800/-	15
4	Loand Suri	10000/-	15
5	Khosa	5500/-	15
6	Leghari	48000/-	20
7	Loand Tibi	2400/-	15
8	Gurchani	12000/-	20
9	Dreshak	8000/-	15
10	Mazari	35750/-	20

11

Later on more additional lands were granted to few Tumandar as following

Srr.#	Name Tumandar	Land
1	Rabnawaz Khetraan	07 Squares
2	Ashiq Muhammad Buzdar	02 Squares
3	K.B.S Raheem Khan	02 Squares
44	Manzor Ahmad Khan Qaisrani	02 Squares
		05 Squares

12

After the emergence of Pakistan, the *Tumandari* system remained in force, finally the federal government, under a decree, announced the abolition of the chieftaincy system from the country, but its roots were ingrained in every sector. Thus the foundations of the revival and evolution of the feudal system in Pakistan remained in the form of tense trees during the imperialist era and despite the passage of seventy years the feudal system remained in Pakistan in all its glory and splendor. The Pakistani government has always looked helpless in the face of this feudal class. Eventually the chieftaincy system was abolished and all its superstitions were abolished. All administrative and judicial powers were abolished and at the same time it was banned that no one could continue such activities. Nor shall any person be allowed to set up any kind of private and private prison or to keep any individual in private

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

slavery or private prison.¹³

The tribes of Dera Ghazi Khan including Khatran, Bazdar, Qaisarani, Lund, Khosa, Leghari, Gurchani, Dareshk, Mazari and many other important allied tribes have been prominent in the social, political and cultural life of Dera Ghazi Khan. These local tribes, based on their numerical strength, have been taking the path of resistance against the rulers of every era. In the Sikh era, the style of resistance in Dera Ghazi Khan was slightly different. The tribe settled matters individually. The head of each tribe was free to settle matters.¹⁴ In Dera Ghazi Khan, the British rule once again ignited the feudal system here. Before their arrival, the land was locally shared by one tribe according to their manpower and each tribe had its own territory. But after the British came here, they formed a group of landlords and tribal chiefs. The people belonging to this group were given a large area of land as property to protect the British interests in their area.¹⁵ Hashim Sher explained that Dera Ghazi Khan was divided into nine *Taman* and the government awarded Jamal Leghari and Bahram Mazari with the title of Khan Bahadur for their loyalty to the government, first on the recommendation of Nawab and then on the recommendation of Sandeman. That's how he opened his mouth.¹⁶

British government gave them political power and this political power was passed down from generation to generation. With the advent of democratic institutions, these feudal lords became the greatest mentors of these institutions and this system flourished under the patronage of the government. Before 1945, these feudal lords were part of the Unionist Party government. After losing the elections in 1945-46, they joined Muslim League shortly before the establishment of Pakistan and became indispensable in electoral politics due to their political influence. They are considered important in democratic politics. Political parties are subjugated to them because without their support because political parties cannot win elections. By taking the administration hostage, its influence has been extended to the common people, as a result of which their power has been curtailed and no one can dare to oppose.¹⁷ From a social point of view, the poor are still in the grip of the feudal system and these tribal chiefs and feudal are representatives. These feudal lords have nothing to do with regional development or the welfare of the people but deprive the people and force them into slavery.¹⁸ Because the government had deliberately created this class. They adopted a strategy of depriving the common man from economic resources at his disposal and instead of regional development; he maintained backwardness and destitution which created terror in his area and people suffered in every possible way was forced.¹⁹ According to Ginkowski, these tribes were the descendants of Baloch chiefs who came to the area to graze their cattle and evict the locals. At the time of the settlement, the local *Tamandars* lost most of the lands of the common people of their nation by getting the ownership record in their names. One of the reasons people were afraid of him was that he had administrative and judicial powers which he was taking unfair advantage and the people were deprived of any kind of legal action.²⁰

When the expansionist ambitions of the imperialist government decided to turn to Balochistan after the War of Independence, they felt some dangers during their advance. They are ready for war. They have no tax system and they give some areas in their area to the local *Jats* for cultivation and collect taxes from them.²¹ As British troops crossed the Indus and advanced westward, their expansionist ambitions became apparent. Ingrī, who had not yet interfered in local affairs, now began to interfere openly. When Robert Sandeman came to

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

Dera Ghazi Khan, he decided to contact the reputable people in the area, finalizing the advance towards the west, and first of all rewarded Nawab Imam Bakhsh Khan Mazari by making him his ally. He was awarded contracts to build canals and roads and recruited people from his tribe.²²

The British gave legal protection to the feudal system and made an agreement with the local chiefs to protect the interests of the government in their respective areas. At the same time, a formal written agreement was written and the feudal system was sealed. The agreement was reached between the tribal chiefs and Robert Sandeman, a representative of the British government. And so this system has been taking root in the society for almost one and a half hundred years. Before the formation of Taman, Sardar was not so powerful. And he was receiving all the financial benefits under the principle of loyalty, while in case of breach of promise, another tandar could be appointed in his place. Due to this fear, Tamandar fulfilled every legitimate and illegitimate wish of the British government and on the other hand, the British government managed to keep the region in poverty, ignorance and backwardness by tearing apart the local alliance.²³

Sandeman mentally prepared the feudal lords to control the people and for this purpose he strengthened his hold on the Baloch area by offering them prizes, privileges and powers. And put into practice the success of his expansionist thinking. One of the key features of his advance towards Balochistan was to conquer the Baloch tribes along the way by uniting them in every way without a fight had to make him-self submissive. Similarly, dividing the existing tribes involved patronizing some of them and subduing others by force. Tribal chiefs were authorized to recruit soldiers for the levy. And his salary was paid by the government. But he will be considered an employee of the tribe. It was necessary to maintain the authority of the Sardar in the area, even if it meant using force. In all these circumstances, the Deputy Commissioner of the district was very powerful and he kept a close eye on Tamandar. After Imam Bakhsh Mazari and the chiefs of the Baloch tribes joined, Dera Ghazi Khan came under the complete influence of the feudal lords.²⁴

Feudal groups in Pakistan have continued to exert their influence through the government bureaucracy, the Armed Forces and the Pakistani political elite. There is no blinking at the fact that five percent feudal are occupying 95 percent of Assemblies and hence they are enjoying key posts not only in provinces but also in Federal Government.²⁵

Social Impacts On The Society.

When Sandeman became the Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan in 1876, he advised the British government to adopt an expansionist policy. And made the tribal chiefs his ally under the Tamandari system. The government benefited from adopting this policy- Under this system, the people were further subjugated under the influence of powerful tribal chiefs, while the chiefs were given privileges and in a way made semi-taxpayers of the government. ²⁶. In order to include Dera Ghazi Khan, especially the tribal area, in its jurisdiction, the people were given barren lands and financial incentives to encourage them to refrain from invasions.²⁷ Together the Deputy Commissioners and the feudal lords radically changed the social system as a result of which the society was divided into classes and the common people began to be exploited.

Huge sums of money were collected from the people. His life was indigestible, the tribal chiefs

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

were given the powers of honorary magistrates and the people were further harassed because these feudal lords were the accused and the judges.²⁸ The feudal lord was very powerful in Dera Ghazi Khan. And the poor people were at his mercy. After the feudal lords were allowed to occupy the public lands, most of the lands became the property of the feudal lords. The British hunted two birds with one stone. That is, he created a privileged class and also controlled the people. The patronage of these feudal lords was the government which caused the common people to suffer social misery. The Zagirdars did not pay any attention to education but deliberately stopped education in their areas so as not to create political consciousness. Educational backwardness puts Dera Ghazi Khan behind other districts. The backwardness and poverty of the people also made the feudal lords politically strong and no one among the subjects saw them as political rivals. Since the establishment of Pakistan, feudal lords have been dominant in electoral politics and have been considered invincible in their constituencies. Therefore, we can say that the feudal system has not only bound the social and political system in its grip, but it is not likely to end yet. We can gauge the political impact of Feudalism from the election results.

Political Impacts On The Society.

Due to ethnic and administrative powers the feudal became a dominant force in the politics of the district before the partition and the politics of the district was under the grip of these feudal as we can observe in the political process. During political reform feudal Dera Ghazi Khan remained the members for the 1st Council of the Governor of Punjab from 1897 to 1920 and member Punjab Legislative Council 1921 to 1936.

Council of the Governor of Punjab

Sr.#	Name	Council of the Governor of Punjab	Year
1	Nawab Sir Imam Bakhsh Mazari	1 st Council of the Governor of Punjab	01-11-1897 to 03-07-1909
2	Nawab Sir Behram Khan Mazari	2 nd Council of the Governor of Punjab	03-01-1910 to 14-12-1912
3	Nawab Sir Behram Khan Mazari	3 rd Council of the Governor of Punjab	04-01-1913 to 19-04-1916
4	Nawab Sir Behram Khan Mazari	4 th Council of the Governor of Punjab	12-06-1916 to 06-04-1920

29

1st Punjab Legislative Council to 4th Punjab Legislative Council 1921-1936

1st Punjab Legislative Council 1921-1923			
Sr.#	Name	Legislative Council	Year
1	Sardar Alan Khan Dareshak	1 st Legislative Council	08-01-1921 to 27-10-1923
2	Nawab Sir Jamal Khan Leghari	1 st Legislative Council	08-01-1921 to 27-10-1923
2nd Punjab Legislative Council 1924-1926			

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

1	Khan Bahadur Sheikh Faiz Muhammad	2 nd Legislative Council	02-01-1924 to 27-10-1926
2	Khan Bahadur Sardar Nawab Sir Muhammad Jamal Khan Leghari	2 nd Legislative Council	02-01-1924 to 27-10-1926
3rd Punjab Legislative Council 1927-1930			
1	Khan Bahadur Sheikh Faiz Muhammad Advocate	3 rd Legislative Council	03-01-1927 to 26-07-1930
2	Khan Bahadur Sardar Nawab Sir Muhammad Jamal Khan Leghari	3 rd Legislative Council	03-01-1927 to 26-07-1930
4th Punjab Legislative Council 1930 to 1936			
1	Sardar Bahadur Khan Dareshak	4 th Legislative Council	24-10-1930 to 10-11-1936
2	Khan Bahadur Sheikh Faiz Muhammad Ad	4 th Legislative Council	24-10-1930 to 10-11-1936
3	Khan Bahadur Sardar Nawab Sir Muhammad Jamal Khan Leghari	4 th Legislative Council	24-10-1930 to 10-11-1936

30

Punjab Legislative Assembly 1937-1945

Sr.#	Name of Feudal	Council of the Governor of Punjab	Year
1	Khan Bahadur Sheikh Faiz Muhammad Advocate	Punjab Legislative Assembly 1937	01-11-1897 to 03-07-1909
2	Khan Bahadur Sardar Nawab Sir Muhammad Jamal Khan Leghari	Punjab Legislative Assembly 1937	03-01-1910 to 14-12-1912
3	Khawaja Ghulam Murtaza	Punjab Legislative Assembly 1937	04-01-1913 to 19-04-1916

31

Elections 1945-1946

D.G Khan Northern	Sr.#	Name Candidate	Party	Position
	1	Atta Muhammad Buzdar	Muslim League	Unopposed Elected
	2	Amir Muhammad Qaisrani	Unionist	Nomination Paper Rejected
	3	Ghazi Muhammad Khan Khosa	Independent	Nomination Paper Rejected

(32)

D.G Khan Central	Sr.#	Name Candidate	Party	Vote	Position
	1	Akhwand Abdul Kareem Advocate	Muslim League	2986	2nd
	2	Sheikh Faiz Muhammad Advocate	Unionist	3655	1st

33

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

D.G Khan Southern	Sr.#	Name Candidate	Party	Vote	Position
	1	Sardar Bahadur Khan	Muslim League	3237	1st
	2	Sardar Ghaus Bakhsh Khan	Unionist	3133	2nd
	3	Gul Muhammad	Independent	27727	3rd
	4	Muhammad Aziz Khan	Independent	0326	4 th

(34)

Emergence of Pakistaan

The feudal are still strong with the help of geo-ethnic based position of electoral constituencies after the emergence of Pakistan. In Dera Ghazi Khan politics is still concentrates on these feudal due to weak political system and political parties. Feudal are mostly the candidates of Political Parties and they changed Party before every election. Due to their vote bank Political Parties often tried to hand-shake with these feudal. Even in 21st century, we look a strong hold and feudal influence in each constituency of Dera Ghazi Khan since 1970 to onward. The election results 1970 to 2018 reflect the impact of feudal system in the politics of Pakistan.

The Geo-Ethnic Position & Nature of the Electoral Constituencies During Election 1970

Sr. No.	NA	PP	Largest Group	2nd Groups	Victorious	Political Party
01	88		Khosa Group	Qaisrani and Khawaja		Jamat-e-Islami
		135	Khetran Group	Buzdar Group	Khetran	IGD
		136	Khosa/Loand	Khawaja/ Qaisrani	Khosa	Jl
		137	Leghari	Khosa/Loand	Leghari	IND
2	89		Leghari	Khosa	Mazari	IND
		138	Leghari	Gurchani/ Khosa	Leghari	IND
		139	Mazari	Dreshak /Others	Mazari	IND
		140	Dareshak	Mazari	Dreshak	IND

Election 1970

NA	PP	Winner	Party	Loser	Party
88		Dr. Nazeer Ahmad	Jl	Khawaja Qutab-u-Din	MJUP
	135	Rab Nawaz Khetran	IGD	Dost Muhammad Buzdar	IND
	136	Atta Muhammad Khosa	Jl	Bashir u Din Salar	PPP
	137	Muhammad Khan Leghari	IND	Molvi M. Akram	MJUP
89		Sherbaz Khan Mazari	IND	Sardar Shaukat Mazari	PPP
	138	Mehmood Khan Leghari	IND	M. Farooq Khan	IND
	139	Mir Balkh Sher	IND	Dur Muhammad Khan	PPP

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

	9	Mazari			
	140	Nasrullah Khan Darishak	IND	M. Kaleem Khan	PPP

35

Geo-Ethnic Position in Election 1977 & 1985

Electi on 1977 & 1985	Sr. #	N A	PP	Major Groups	Second Groups	Area/ Tehsils	Winne r	Par ty
	1	124		Khosa/ Qaisrani	Buzdar Khawaja	Taunsa/D.G. Khan	Other	PNA
			184	Khosa	Leghari	D.G. Khan	Other	PPP
			185	Leghari	Khosa	D.G. Khan	Leghar i	PPP
			186	Leghari	Khosa	D.G. Khan	Other	PPP
	2	125		Leghari/Khos a	Loand/Buzda r	D.G.Khan /Jampur	Leghar i	PPP
			189	Buzdar	Khetran/ot hers	Tribal Area	Buzdar	PPP
			190	Khosa/	Loand	D.G Khan	Khosa	PPP
	3	126		Mazari	Dareshak/ot hers	Rajanpur	Mazari	PPP
			187	Dareshak	Leghari/ Pitafi	Jampur	Daresh ak	PPP
			188	Dareshak	Mazari/Other s	Rajanpur	Mazari	PPP

Positions of in Elections 1988, 1990, 1993 & 1997

Electi on 1988-1997	N A	P P	Major Groups	Second Groups	Area/ Tehsils	Winner	Winnin g Occasio ns
	132		Khosa/ Qaisrani	Khawaja/ Buzdar	Taunsa/D GK	Khawaja/ Khosa	2+2
		19	Qaisrani, Khawaja	Buzdars, Khetran	D.G. Khan	Qaisrani/Kha	2+2

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

	9				waja	
	200	Khosa	Loand/Buzdar	D.G. Khan	Khosa	04
133		Leghari	Khosa	D.G. Khan	Leghari	04
	201	Khosa	Leghari	D.G.K. City	Buzdar	04
	202	Leghari	Leghari	D.G Khan	Khosa	04
	203	Leghari	Leghari	D.G Khan		04

36

Results of Elections 2002, 2008 and 2013 National Assembly Elections

Election 2002			Election 2008		Election 2013	
N A	Winner	Runner Up	Winner	Runner	Winner	Runner Up
171	Khawaja Sheraz Mehmmod	Amjad Farooq Khosa	Khawaja Sheraz Mehmmod	Amjad Farooq Khosa	Amjad Farooq Khosa	Khawaja Sheraz Mehmmod
172	Farooq Ahmad Leghari	Muhammad Khan Leghari	Farooq Ahmad Leghari	Hafiz Abdul Kareem	Hafiz Abdul Kareem	Jamal Khan Leghari
173	Awes Ahmad Leghari	Husain Khan Leghari	Saif-udin Khosa	Awes Ahmad Leghari	Awes Ahmad Leghari	Saif-u-Din Khosa

37

Comparative Analysis of General Election 2002, 2008 and 2013 of Provincial Assembly

Election 2002			Election 2008		Election 2013	
PP	Winner	Runner Up	Winner	Runner Up	Winner	2nd
240	Mir Badshah Qaisrani	Imam Bakhsh Qaisrani	Mir Badshah Qaisrani	Javed Iqbal Qaisrani	Mir Badshah Qaisrani	Khawaja Daud

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

24 1	Fatih M. Buzdar	Khwaja M. Mudasir	Fatih M. Buzdar	Khwaja Nizam Mulk	Khwaja Nizam	Usman Buzdar
24 2	Javed Akhtar Loand	Salahudin Khosa	Amjad Khosa	Javed Akhtar Loand	Javed Akhtar Loand	Mohsin Ata Khosa
24 3	M. Khan Leghari	Jafar Khan Leghari	Saif-u-Din Khosa	Awes Khan Leghari	Ahmad Ali Dreshak	Saif-u-Din Khosa
24 4	Abdul Aleem Shah	Saif-u-Din Khosa	Dost M. Khosa	Abdul Aleem Shah	Abdul Aleem Shah	Akhwand Humayu
24 5	Farooq Ahmad Leghari	Muhamma d Leghari	Mohsin Khan Leghari	Muhammad Khan Leghari	Jamal Khan Leghari	Muhammad Khan Leghari
24 6	Yousaf Khan Leghari	Saif-u-din Khosa	Yousaf Khan Leghari	Rashid Kamran Malana	Mehmood Qadir Leghari	Rashid Malana

Election Result 2018

NA	Winner	Party	Runner Up	Party
18 9	Khawaja Sheraz Mehmmod	PTI	Mir Badsha Qaisrani	PMLN
19 0	Sardar Amjad Farooq Khan Khosa	IND	Sardar Zulfiqar Ali Khan Khosa	PTI
19 1	Zartaj Gul	PTI	Sardar Awes Ahmad Khan Leghari	PMLN
19 2	Sardar Muhammad Khan Leghari	PTI	Muhammad Shahbaz Sharief	PMLN

Provincial Assembly Election-2018

PP	Winner	Part y	Runner Up	Party
28 5	Khawaja Muhammad Daud	PTI	Mir Badhah Qaisrani	PMLN
28 6	Usman Ahmad Khan Buzdar	PTI	Khwaja Nizam uul Mahmood	PPP
28 7	Sardar Javed Akhtar Khan Loand	PTI	Sardar Mohsin Atta Khosa	IND
28	Sardar Mohsin Atta Khosa		Sardar Muuhammad Sauf-u-Din	PTI

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

8		IND	Khosa	
28	Muhammad Hanif Pitafi		Dr.Shaheena Kareem	PTI
9		IND		
29	Sardar Ahmad Ali Khan	PTI	Muhammad Ahmad Khan Leghari	PMLN
0	Dareshak			
29	Sardar Mohyudin Khan Khosa	PTI	Mahmood Qadir Khan Leghari	PMLN
1				
29	Sardar Muhammad Khan	PTI	Sardar Awes Ahmad Khan	PMLN
2	Leghari		Leghari	

38

Conclusion

The feudal system which flourished in France and Britain, starting with the ancient Roman Empire in Europe, spread its claws in different countries of the world. In the subcontinent, this system is seen in somewhat different periods, but this system got its real boost due to the occupation of the subcontinent by the imperialist system. After which the expansionist policy of the British played a key role in its development was Sandemann's efforts, the divide and rule policy was successful. As a result, the people were subjugated by the feudal lords. This system affected the lives of the common people, especially the economic situation, which led to the promotion of social stratification. Even by the time of the establishment of Pakistan, this system had become deeply ingrained in the people. Thus the feudal system has for a long time been able to maintain its regular dominance over the people of Dera Ghazi Khan. If we look at the present day, the effects of the feudal system still prevail on the land of Dera Ghazi Khan. I have the opportunity to contest elections where the number of members of my tribe is in the thousands and most of the people belonging to the tribe must have racial and tribal prejudice in front of them. It is almost impossible to participate. The main reason for this is the lack of performance and popularity of political parties in Dera Ghazi Khan District as these political parties still do not have candidates to compete with these feudal lords in electoral politics. It is clear that the personal vote bank of the tribe in every constituency is the guarantor of its success. The concept of Sardar in the tribe still exists today and due to racial prejudice, each tribe supports its own tribal chief. In the National Assembly and Provincial Assembly constituencies, the Sardar family member of almost every tribe is a candidate in the election or the candidate selected by the Sardar participates in the election and voting for him is considered a collective decision of the tribe. It is considered and its honor and respect is obligatory on every member of the tribe. An example of this is the election of the provincial constituency PP-240. This area is Taman Qaisarani. From here Sardar Manzoor Ahmad Khan Qaisarani continued to win the elections and then his son Sardar Zahoor Ahmad Qaisarani won the elections. After his death, his son Mir Badshah continued to win the election. Recently, his wife won the election on his seat after being disqualified from the court. But even after his disqualification, a common man of the same tribe won the election by fielding a candidate for Tamandar, which shows the influence of the feudal lords in the electoral politics of the constituency. It is not easy to break the shackles of tribal politics and community politics, and the feudal lords in the area have a clear advantage over their political opponents. And the biggest reason for this is the low level of literacy rate. Finally, the feudal chiefs in Dera Ghazi Khan are so influential that they have direct influence

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

of administration and possess skills to solve people's problems of court and police station, these feudal plays their role to end these cases and play the role of mediatory in the cases of murder and other heinous crimes. They even pressurize their political opponents and provide shelters to outlaws and use them for their own personal interests. People consider it privilege to invite feudal to their moments of celebrations and pay them a comprehensive protocol. In the recent past, Feudal used to get votes via messages but this system has become weaker. On the whole, but Feudal are still dominant and influential in the electoral politics of District Dera Ghazi Khan.

1880 کی ایک دستاویزات میں ڈیرہ قازیخان کے تمام سرداران اور رئیسوں کے دستخط جمعہ

Socio-Political Impacts of Feudalism on Saraiki Dera Ghazi Khan

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